

Relevance of Time Management Skills to Students Classroom Performance

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ABSTRACT

Time Management skills serves as a help for the students classroom performance, making it more important for them to apply in the future. Since it is the most important in terms of our daily living, this study aimed to identify the relevance of time management skills to students classroom performance of the Senior High School Students of St. Paul University Surigao. This study applied the quantitative research design employing a descriptive survey technique with 272 participants. The main instrument employed in gathering necessary data was the researcher-made questionnaire. The gathered data were treated using frequency count and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results showed that there is no significant difference in the relevance of time management skills to students classroom performance according to their grade, sex, and gender. The research results could serve as background knowledge and framework for future researchers who will be doing deeper investigations that are similar to this study.

KEYWORDS: *Time Management skills, Classroom Performance, Survey*

INTRODUCTION

Many students often overlook the relevance of time management to their classroom performance thus affecting critically their academic performance after the pandemic. When the pandemic occurs students lifestyle drastically changed and the education system heavily suffered to change, there have been issues with the implementation of distance learning, including the following: students cannot be fully supervised by the subject teacher during learning activities at home, students are late in collecting drawing assignments according to deadlines, and students are unable to manage online learning time effectively (Ilhamdaniah, Megayanti, 2021).

Students were forced to online distance-learning, study independently and adopt to the new grading system, as almost everything was online and some student are staying up late and actively online, of the most typical challenges for different learners taking online classes is time management. Students may struggle to organize their time, as well as know when to transition their attention from one subject to another, in the absence of physical borders or physical location changes. Thus, the sleeping schedule and routine of the students changed to the new normal (Gaddi et al., 2024).

Time management is a crucial skill to utilize in students classroom performance, as what Sofia Auld (2019) stated that effective time management reduces stress as it produces a sense of achievement or satisfaction as fulfilling the items from their objectives on time with less time, and more time with your friends, family and other hobbies. Therefore, enhancing students time management skills to their classroom performance can lead them to their academic excellence. As cited by (Alyami et al 2021) Individuals can use time management to control time and their activities as the key to success. Considering with such skill, achieving academic excellence in students classroom performance is not a hard task.

With that in mind, after 3 years of students distance learning almost all the school here the Philippines are back into full face to face learning and blended learning like St. Paul University Surigao.

Classroom performance to evaluation of academic performance is monitored again. Which means, students are forced again to change back to the normal way of face to face learning, like waking up early to go to school, passing assignments directly, doing house chores after school, activities in the schools and many more. The students are adopting again to the normal learning, their schedule has changed after the long distance learning.

This study aims to identify the relevance of time management skills to students' classroom performance, specifically focusing on the impact of time blocking, time tracking, and to-do lists. For this reason, the researcher chose the senior high school students as participants, as this research aims to identify how time management skills contributes to their classroom performance. The findings of this study can provide insights into the development of educational strategies that promotes how important time management, leading to improved classroom performance.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study was anchored on the theory of Wright (2002) entitled "Pickle Jar Theory". The pickle jar theory is based on a time management skill that would help us to do our academic responsibilities as a student.

Wright's theory posits three effective time management techniques to implement the Pickle Jar Theory. This approach proves successful in mitigating procrastination and maintaining control over your workload by strategically allocating fixed time blocks for distinct activities. Given the constant demands of work, family, social commitments, and personal pursuits, it is easy to lose sight of time, a finite and valuable resource. Recognizing the significance of tracking time, the pickle jar theory encourages the identification of priority tasks, allowing for the creation of a practical to-do list. This approach also enables the ability to defer or delegate tasks that may not hold immediate importance (Wright 2002).

The variables in the first box encompass the key characteristics of respondent's profile, including grade level, strand, and sex, which are crucial factors in assessing the relevance of time management skills in relation to student's classroom performance.

Grade level typically refers to the educational level of a student is expected to have reached based on their age or academic progress.

Strand typically refers to a specific area or category of learning within a curriculum. Strands are organized around overarching themes or topics and are designed to help students develop a comprehensive understanding of a particular subject area.

Sex refers to the biological identity of a person, typically categorized as male or female.

The second box includes the time management skills that is relevance to students classroom performance. These are: Time Blocking, Time Tracking and To Do List.

Time Blocking is a type of time management technique in which people set aside specific times of the day for various jobs or activities. This method gives people the ability to set priorities for their work, reduce outside distractions, and keep a disciplined schedule for efficient time management.

Time Tracking refers to the practice of monitoring and recording how time is spent on various activities throughout the day. According to (Nasrulla et al., 2021) time tracking contributes to students' self-organization, motivation, and development of independence, ultimately benefiting their academic achievements and overall success in their classroom performance.

To Do List is a method involves creating a list with tasks prioritized on a scale to streamline execution (Tarina 2023). This time management technique is important as this will help the students to manage their time for the students to improve their classroom performance.

METHOD

This study applied the quantitative research design employing a descriptive survey technique with 272 Senior High School students. The researchers used a simple random sampling method in conducting the study. The main instrument employed in gathering the necessary data was the researcher-made questionnaire, validated by experts. The first part of the data questionnaire contains the students profile, such as Grade, Strand, and Sex. While the second part includes the time management skills that would be of use to their classroom performance.

Before administering the questionnaire, a letter-request was sent to the School Head of Senior High School Department of St. Paul University Surigao to ask for the permission to conduct the test. The researchers administered the questionnaire through a survey during face to face class to the participants with the help of the teachers and advisers. Afterwards, it was retrieved, analyzed, and interpreted using statistical tools. The statistical tools used are frequency count and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation, and analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result and discussion of the data. The presented data corresponds to the order of the problems cited in the statement of problem; Profile of the participants, and time management skills that would be of use to the students classroom performance.

Table 1. *Profile of the Participant*

Profile	f (272)	%
Grade level		
11	141	51.84
12	131	48.16
Strand		
ABM	43	15.81
STEM	142	52.21
HUMSS	66	24.2
ADT/TVL	21	7.72
Sex		
Male	101	37.13
Female	171	62.87

As to the grade level most of them are in Grade 11 with the number of 141 (51.84%) then Grade 12 students with 131(48.16%). With regards to their *strand* most of them belong to STEM or Science,

Technology, Engineering and Mathematics with the total of 142(52.21%), then HUMSS or Humanities and social sciences strand with 66 (24.25%). As for ABM or Accountancy, Business, and management the strand has a total of 43 (15.81%); and lastly the ADT/TVL or Arts, Design Track/Technical Vocational and Livelihood with 21(7.72%). As to their sex, among the 272 participants of the study, most were females 171 (62.87%) then males is 101(37.13%).

Table 2. *Relevance of Time Management Skills to Students Classroom Performance in terms of Time blocking.*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
Time Blocking				
I use time blocking when				
1. I juggle to many different performance task/ responsibilities.	2.79	0.89	O	R
2. I spend too much time using my gadget for my assignments and using it for leisure.	2.91	0.87	O	R
3. I battle for constant interruptions throughout the day.	2.85	0.87	O	R
4. I struggle to find the time and Mental space for big picture throughout the day.	2.80	0.90	O	R
5. I set boundaries and allocate time or both studies and personal activities	2.83	0.94	O	R
Average:	2.83	0.89	O	R

Rating Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Always</i>	A	<i>Highly Relevant</i>	HR
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Often</i>	O	<i>Relevant</i>	R
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Sometimes</i>	S	<i>Less Relevant</i>	LR
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Never</i>	N	<i>Not Relevant</i>	NR

Table 2 displays the relevance of time management skills to students' classroom performance in terms of Time Blocking. In general, it is verbally interpreted as *Often* and is qualitatively described as *Relevant* (M=2.83, SD=0.89).

This implies that students find time blocking commonly relevant for managing various tasks and responsibilities. They would often use this technique in their daily lives as students to achieve their goals and to have good classroom performance. In addition, the findings from the research conducted by Hakoune (2023) it indicates that time blocking is a productivity technique where students divide their day into specific time slots dedicated to particular tasks. This method can allow students to focus on distinct activities in each block, increasing productivity and concentration on students' tasks.

Many students struggle, especially in managing their time, and this is one of the reasons for procrastination, late submission, and even forgotten schoolwork and personal tasks. With so many distractions around, it is imperative that students make conscious attempts to sharpen their attention. As time passes by, seconds turn into minutes, minutes into hours, hours into days, days into weeks, and weeks with assignments and duties not performed. As Araujo (2022) stated, they will probably discover that they have spent more time doing "nothing". In other words, lacking in time management can negatively impact students' classroom performance.

Among the 5 indicators, the item "I spend too much time using my gadgets for my assignments and using it for leisure" got the highest mean ($M=2.91$, $SD= 0.87$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This means that most of the students often use their time using gadgets or electronic devices not only for their assignments but also for leisure or enjoyment.

The study by Agrojaya (2018) shows that technology can help students interact with classmates more easily and positively, have access to extracurricular learning resources, and learn more about technology. However, Pubgenius (2024) argues that using technology excessively can have unfavorable effects. Furthermore, adolescents who are dependent on electronic devices may encounter emotional and behavioral issues, including erratic behavior, irrational feelings, and explosive emotions, and they might grow self-absorbed, losing sight of their surroundings and crucial facets of life, like studying and getting enough sleep.

Therefore, it is important for us to use gadgets responsibly and not only for fun because gadgets will be a good benefit to us only if we know how to use them and using them excessively will not only affect our classroom performance but also our health, which is the most important of all.

On the other hand, the item "I juggle to many different performance tasks/responsibilities" got the lowest mean ($M=2.79$, $SD= 0.89$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This discusses regularly, it is for students to manage multiple tasks and responsibilities related to school activities and possibly in various areas or aspects of their life. Being a student does not mean that they only have schoolwork that needs to be done on time, they also have their own personal life that needs attention and time.

According to Biyoyo et al. (2024), the difficulty of handling several responsibilities at once is referred to as "juggling multiple tasks and responsibilities." It is similar to trying to balance on a high wire when mistakes could have serious repercussions. By juggling too much, one can be prone to mistakes because you cannot focus only on one thing, and it is most likely getting confused over time because of the multiple tasks that need to be done.

A Research conducted by Dalrymple (2023) shows that by steering clear of distractions and abstaining from multitasking, they can expedite the completion of their daily responsibilities. This highlights the importance for students to effectively manage their time and refrain from multitasking to minimize the likelihood of making errors. It underscores the notion that completing tasks quickly is insignificant if it results in numerous mistakes.

Table 3. *Relevance of Time Management Skills to Students Classroom Performance in terms of tracking time*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
Tracking Time				
I use time tracking when				
1. I monitor how much time I spend studying for different subjects.	2.78	0.89	O	R
2. I am working on long-term projects or assignments to prevents last-minute rushes and promotes better project management.	2.76	0.84	O	R
3. I prepare for exam to allocate sufficient time to review each subject or topic, ensuring comprehensive coverage and reducing the risk of cramming.	2.78	0.86	O	R
4. I estimate how much time it takes to complete homework assignments.	2.70	0.94	O	R

5. I participate in extracurricular activities alongside with my academic commitments	2.79	0.89	O	R
Average:	2.76	0.89	O	R

Rating Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Always</i>	A	<i>Highly Relevant</i>	HR
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Often</i>	O	<i>Relevant</i>	R
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Sometimes</i>	S	<i>Less Relevant</i>	LR
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Never</i>	N	<i>Not Relevant</i>	NR

Table 3 displays the relevance of time management skills to students' classroom performance in terms of Time Tracking. On average, it is verbally interpreted as *Often* and is qualitatively described as *Relevant* (M=2.76, SD=0.89). This indicates that students noted how much time they spend on various tasks throughout the day.

Time tracking does not only improve the flow of time for students but also enhances academic writing, ensuring a nearly flawless outcome. The study by Dudley (2022) shows that by revealing distractions and encouraging time batching, time monitoring aids in producing excellent papers without the need for multitasking skills. Additionally, it helps meet deadlines by setting strict project timelines, breaking the cycle of rushed work, and allowing for effective editing.

As Biter (2021) stated, time tracking has its fundamentals in productivity, gaining valuable insights, and maintaining a smooth workflow. This applies to everyone in an organization or society, regardless of whether you are an executive, a manager, or a team member. Therefore, keeping track of your time is of utmost importance.

Among the 5 indicators, the item "I participate in extracurricular activities alongside with my academic commitments" got the highest mean (M=2.79, SD=0.89), which can be verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This implies that students often use time tracking to participate simultaneously in their extracurricular activities and academic commitments, thus having a conflicting schedule or smooth flow of time in participating in both extracurricular activities and academic commitments.

As scrutinized by Muhammad (2017), proficiency in time management is a skill that enables an individual to regulate their schedule, ultimately enhancing their performance in specific roles, such as students in their extracurricular activities and their academic commitments.

Furthermore, the item "I estimate how much time it takes to complete homework assignments" got the lowest mean (M=2.70, SD=0.94), which can be verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This suggests that students frequently apply tracking time as a method for time management in noting how much time it takes to complete their homework assignments to have a better classroom performance.

According to Dudley (2022), utilizing time tracking for completing homework assignments helps meet deadlines and allows more time for other activities. Moreover, time tracking reduces burnout by incorporating rest schedules, preventing fatigue as it assists in planning the day efficiently, allocating sufficient time for other activities.

Table 4. *Relevance of Time Management Skills to Students Classroom Performance in terms of to do list*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
To Do List				
1. I keep track of upcoming assignment, projects, and deadlines.	2.92	0.94	O	R
2. I break down my study sessions into specific task and prioritize subjects based on upcoming exams or assignments.	2.78	0.86	O	R
3. I plan for my day efficiently especially allocating time for classes, study sessions, extracurricular activities and personal commitments.	2.78	0.83	O	R
4. I review specific topics, practice problems, and reinforce their understanding of course material	2.85	0.94	O	R
5. I manage personal task, such As grocery shopping, laundry And other chores	2.91	0.94	O	R
Average:	2.85	0.89	O	R

Rating Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Always</i>	A	<i>Highly Relevant</i>	HR
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Often</i>	O	<i>Relevant</i>	R
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Sometimes</i>	S	<i>Less Relevant</i>	LR
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Never</i>	N	<i>Not Relevant</i>	NR

Table 4 displays the relevance of time management skills to students' classroom performance in terms of a to-do list. On average, it is verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant* (M=2.85, SD= 0.88). This implies that students are regularly organized, competent, and capable of finishing their academic tasks, leading to good productivity and better performance in the classroom.

In the field of time management, an individual's ability to capably use time to achieve important tasks is crucial. One method used to incorporate time management into daily routines is the use of a to-do list. Additionally, according to Tarina (2023), this method involves creating a list ranked by importance to enhance efficiency in their completion

Among the 5 indicators, the item "I keep track of upcoming assignments, projects, and deadlines" got the highest mean (M=2.92, SD=0.94), which can be verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This means that students often track their tasks and deadlines as a significant and necessary practice for their academic performance. Even self-proclaimed procrastinators, like Zaluski (2023), find that to-do lists aid in completing tasks and achieving goals. This simple yet effective tool helps with managing tasks, allowing students to prioritize and organize items according to urgency, importance, and dependencies, making the process much more manageable.

As well, Table 4 represents two lowest means. First, the item "I break down my study sessions into specific tasks and topics that can make studying more manageable and prioritize subjects based on

upcoming exams or assignments." got the lowest mean ($M=2.78$, $SD= 0.86$), with an interpretation of *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This suggests that some students think that it is important to plan their day, setting aside time for studying, activities, and personal commitments.

Also the item "I plan for my day efficiently, especially allocating time for classes, study sessions, extracurricular activities, and personal commitments," got the lowest mean ($M=2.78$, $SD= 0.83$), with an interpretation of *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This suggests that students oftentimes put in use the to do list in managing their time in class or studying of sessions for their exam or assignments, other extracurricular activities and personal commitments.

According to Shadav (2019), making a reliable and accurate estimate of the time required for tasks is the most challenging part of to do lists. People sometimes tend to plan one hour for a task that ends up taking two hours. In order to avoid confusion, it's helpful to give an exact time estimate when listing a top-down activity or to-do list. Although the tasks remain the same, the act of making a list has a psychological impact that helps the brain reduce stress associated with remembering every detail. Additionally Jenifer(2022) suggests that change in mindset allows individuals to enter thinking mode, which makes it easier to prioritize and organize tasks based on their urgency.

Table 5. Summary table of the relevance of time management skills to students classroom Performance

Skills	M	SD	VI	QD
Time Blocking	2.83	0.89	O	R
Time Tracking	2.76	0.89	O	R
To do list	2.81	0.89	O	R
General Average	2.81	0.89	O	R

Rating Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	Always	A	Highly Relevant	HR
3	2.50-3.24	Often	O	Relevant	R
2	1.75-2.49	Sometimes	S	Less Relevant	LR
1	1.00-1.74	Never	N	Not Relevant	NR

Among the skills, *Time Blocking* received the highest mean ($M =2.83$, $SD = 0.89$), which can verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. This implies that time blocking demonstrates that students recognize its effectiveness in managing tasks and responsibilities efficiently. By allocating specific time slots to different activities, students can improve their focus, productivity, and overall organization, leading to a more successful academic experience.

As what Hakoune (2023) stated, that time blocking makes students more productive by dividing their day that allows them to prioritize the most important activity thus increasing productivity and concentration on individual activity. Many students struggle, particularly with time management, leading to issues such as procrastination, late submissions, and forgetting tasks.

In a world filled with distractions, it's crucial for students to actively work on improving their focus. Time slips away quickly, and without mindful attention, students may find themselves spending more time on unproductive activities but in applying time management it permits students to concentrate solely on one task, providing a sense of control and reducing stress (Gaddi et al., 2024).

However, *Time Tracking* got the lowest mean ($M= 2.76$, $SD= 0.89$), Which can be verbally interpreted as *Often* and qualitatively described as *Relevant*. Time tracking notes the time they allocate

to different tasks during the day, recognizing its importance for avoiding procrastination and achieving satisfactory results in their classroom performance.

In addition, time tracking not only enhances students' time management but also improves their academic writing, leading to nearly flawless outcomes. Students frequently employ time tracking as a method for managing their time, aiming to achieve success academically as well as in their daily household tasks and societal engagements, and even in their future careers (Gaddi et al., 2024). Time tracking is fundamental to productivity, offering valuable insights and ensuring a seamless workflow.

Students often use time tracking to balance their activities to their classroom in which can lead to either a conflict in their schedule or smooth time management it also emphasizes that proficiency in time management enhances performance in various roles, such as academics and extracurriculars activities Muhammad (2017). It allows students to monitor how they spend their time, helping them identify areas for improvement and make informed decisions about task prioritization. This method not only aids in avoiding procrastination but also ensures timely completion of assignments and projects, contributing to a more satisfying and rewarding academic journey.

Table 6. Significant difference in the time management skills to students classroom performance in terms of their profile

Profile	Dependent	F	Sig.	Decision
Grade	Time Blocking	2.14	0.144	Do not reject H ₀
	Tracking Time	1.65	0.200	Do not reject H ₀
	To do list	0.95	0.330	Do not reject H ₀
Strand	Time Blocking	0.73	0.536	Do not reject H ₀
	Tracking Time	0.27	0.847	Do not reject H ₀
	To do list	0.11	0.953	Do not reject H ₀
Sex	Time Blocking	0.00	0.980	Do not reject H ₀
	Tracking Time	0.14	0.713	Do not reject H ₀
	To do list	1.68	0.196	Do not reject H ₀

Table 6 presents significant difference on the time management skills to students classroom performance in terms of *time blocking*, *time tracking* and to do list when they are grouped according to their profile such as *grade*, *strand*, *sex*

In terms of *grade*, it reveals that there are no significant differences on time managements skills to student's classroom performance in terms of time blocking (p-value =0.114), time tracking (p-value=0.200) and to do list (p-value=0.330). Considering that respective computed p-value are higher than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to not rejecting the hypothesis. This means that the relevance to time management skills to students classroom performance in terms of time blocking, time tracking, and to do list do not significantly differ when it comes to their Grade.

The findings also revealed that the students' gender differences have no effect on their classroom performance. This suggest that regardless of your grade, it won't affect the relevance of time management skills to the students classroom performance. Thus, while our study could not confirm that grade can affect the relevance of time management skills to students classroom performance, it did confirm the finding of other studies.

Research indicates that the grade level of a student does impact their time management skills and academic performance. As students progress to higher grade levels, their time management skills tend to improve, leading to a positive correlation between time management skills and academic achievement. Nevertheless, it contrasts to a certain study as stated by Cyril, (2015) The grade of a student does not significantly impact the relevance of time management skills to classroom performance in terms of time blocking, time tracking, and academic achievement. Research indicates that good time

management skills are crucial for students to plan ahead, prioritize assignments, and avoid procrastination, leading to academic success.

In terms of their strand, it reveals that there are no significant differences on time management skills to student's classroom performance in terms of time blocking (p -value=0.536), time tracking (p -value=0.847) and to do list (p -value=0.953). Considering that respective computed p -value are higher than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to not rejecting the hypothesis.

Time management skills are essential for students to manage their curriculum effectively and achieve learning objectives, leading to positive academic outcomes. By effectively managing their time, students can allocate sufficient focus and effort to each subject or task, ensuring a balanced approach to their studies. This skill enables students to prioritize assignments, projects, and study sessions, leading to a more organized and structured approach to learning. With proper time management, students can avoid last-minute cramming, reduce stress levels, and improve their overall academic performance. Ultimately, mastering time management empowers students to achieve their learning objectives efficiently, leading to positive academic outcomes and setting a strong foundation for future success.

Studies have shown a positive association between greater academic achievement and effective time management skills among students in various fields, emphasizing the importance of these skills for academic success. Alyami, et al. (2021).

In terms of *Sex*, it reveals that there are no significant differences on the relevance of time management skills to students classroom performance in terms of *time blocking* (p -value=980), *time tracking* (p -value=0713), and *to do list* (p -value=0.196) as to their sex considering that respective computed p -value are higher than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to not rejecting the hypothesis. This means that the relevance of time management skills to students classroom performance do not significantly differ when it comes to their sex. That regardless of the sex of students, they may be male or female, The findings also revealed that the students' gender differences have no effect on time management skills to the students classroom performance.

This suggest that regardless of if you are a male or female student, it won't affect your classroom performance. Sex and students classroom performance was found to have no significant effect to the relevance of time management skills to their classroom performance.

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that, the relevance of time management skills to students classroom performance in terms of time blocking, time tracking, and to do list are often relevant to the senior high school students. This study also concludes that there is no significant difference between grade level, strand and sex and the time management specifically, Time Blocking, Time Tracking and To Do List.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are based on the conclusion of the study:

1. For the Senior high school students to improve their time management skills, students can use the time management technique that is used to conduct this study, which is the time blocking, time tracking and use to-do lists. Students can also take regular breaks, reflect, and adjust their strategies, and seek support when needed.
2. For the teachers who is one of the experts on time managements, they can offer valuable guidance and tips to students seeking to enhance their time management abilities. By sharing

their expertise, they can assist students in effectively managing their time, leading to improved performance in the classroom.

3. For the parents they can play an integral role in fostering their children's academic success by equipping them with guidance to effectively manage their time. This includes offering support and assistance in striking a balance between academic and personal responsibilities.
4. Future researchers stand to gain invaluable insights from this study, as it serves as a foundational reference point for conducting similar investigations. Thus, this study not only contributes to current understanding but also lays the groundwork for continued exploration and advancement in the relevant area of study.

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